

Noun Phrase Recognition in Marathi Sentences: Experimental study

Dr. Hemlata Godbole; Dr. Anjani Kumar Ray
Mahatma Gandhi International Hindi University, Wardha (Maharashtra)

Abstract :

Noun Phrase Recognition, also known as NP chunking, involves identifying and classifying sequences of words that function as noun phrases. Noun Phrase (NP) recognition is a crucial task in Natural Language Processing (NLP), providing foundation for various higher-level linguistic tasks such as machine translation, information extraction and syntactic parsing.

Marathi is morphologically rich and syntactically flexible Indo-Aryan language. While substantial work has been done for English and other resource-rich languages, Indian languages like Marathi pose unique challenges due to rich morphology, free word order and agglutinative features.

This paper explores noun phrase recognition in Marathi. This paper presents an algorithm for identifying noun phrases in Marathi language sentences. Based on this algorithm, a computational model has been developed which identifies noun phrases from a given sentence. The rule-based system with the approach of Local Word Grouping has been applied in the process of identifying noun phrases. This task can help in phrase structured based machine translation and thus identifying noun phrases can become the base for other Indian languages. We present an overview of the linguistic structure of noun phrases in Marathi, challenges in automatic recognition, and computational techniques employed. We evaluate both rule-based and machine learning-based approaches.

Keywords: noun phrase, local word group, rule based

Introduction: In this paper, we investigate NP recognition in Marathi language by analyzing its syntactic structure, morphological complexity, and the applicability of various computational approaches. Identification of noun phrases makes the task of Local Word Grouping and NER.

1. Linguistic Features of Marathi

Marathi is spoken by over 83 million people, primarily in the Indian state of Maharashtra. It is a SOV (Subject-Object-Verb) structure language with extensive inflectional morphology. In Marathi, just like in English, a noun phrase (नाम वाक्कांश) is a group of words that functions as a noun in a sentence. It typically includes a noun (नाम) as its head and can be accompanied by modifiers like adjectives (ववशेषण), determiners (वनाारक) although Marathi doesn't have articles like "a" or "the" in English, it has **demonstratives and quantifiers** that function similar to determiners (वनाारक) in English language, possessives (सांबावाचक), and other nouns acting as modifiers.

Morphological Characteristics

1. Case markers (व्यवहारीक): e.g., ला (la), ने (ne), चा (chā), स (sa)
2. Number and gender inflections : मुलगा, मुलगी, मूलगे
3. Compound nouns and postpositional phrases : लाल जुनी गाडी, झाडाच्या मागचे घर etc

Nouns in Marathi (नाम/Nām) name, people, places, things, or ideas. They are inflected for gender (masculine, feminine, neuter), number (singular, plural), and case (nominative, accusative, dative, oblique, vocative) which reflects their role in a sentence. Marathi nouns can be broadly classified into **proper nouns** (व्यक्तिवाचक नाम/ Vyaktivaachak Nām) that name specific entities, and **common nouns** (सामान्य नाम/ Saamaanya Nām) referring to general items or concepts.

Gender in Marathi Nouns

There are three Marathi nouns genders: masculine, feminine, and neuter.

- **Masculine Nouns:** Often end in aa/आ consonant. Example: “मुलगा” (Mulagaa/boy).
- **Feminine Nouns:** Usually end in “ी”/ī. Example: “मुलगी” (Mulagī/girl).
- **Neuter Nouns:** Can end in अ/“a”. Example: “पान” (paan/page).

Number: Singular and Plural Forms

The plural form of Marathi nouns is typically formed by changing the ending of the singular form. The specific change can vary depending on the noun’s gender and ending.

1. **Masculine to Plural:** Add “ी” (ē) or other changes. Example: “वकडा” (Kidaa/insect) becomes “वकडे” (kide/insects).
2. **Feminine to Plural:** Change “ी” (ī) to “या” (yā). Example: “खुची” (khurchi, chair) becomes “खुच्या” (khurchyā, chairs).
3. **Neuter to Plural:** Often involves vowel changes or adding a suffix. Example: “पुस्तक” (Pustak, book) becomes “पुस्तके” (Pustakē, books).

Cases in Marathi Nouns

Marathi employs seven cases to indicate the grammatical and relational function of nouns within sentences.

1. **Nominative Case (प्रथमा, Prathamā):** The subject of the sentence.
2. **Accusative Case (द्वितीया, Dvitiyā):** The direct object.
3. **Instrumental Case (तृतीया, Tṛtīyā):** Means by which or with whom an action is performed.
4. **Dative Case (चतुर्थी, Caturthī):** The indirect object or recipient.
5. **Ablative Case (पांचमी, Pañcamī):** Indicates separation.
6. **Genitive Case (षष्ठी, Ṣaṣṭhī):** Shows possession.
7. **Locative Case (सप्तमी, Saptamī):** Indicates location.

2. Challenges in Noun Phrase Recognition in Marathi

1. **Morphological Richness:** Single-word inflections encode multiple grammatical features.
2. **Free Word Order:** Variable phrase order complicates pattern for recognition.
3. **Ambiguity:** Words may serve multiple grammatical roles.
4. Limited annotated corpora for Marathi.
- 5.

Noun Phrase Structure

While defining noun phrase, Halliday (1997:7) said that “A noun can be accompanied by its determiner and any other modifier.” In this, determiner and any modifier are optional elements of noun phrase whereas noun word is an essential element of any noun phrase. Without it, noun phrase cannot be imagined. Elements of noun phrase are in a particular order. Change in the order of its elements can happen according to interlinguistic rules.

In a sentence, there are fixed places for the subject, object, complement, indeclinable and verb etc. where noun, adjective, verb, adverb etc. are used and play a specific role in the sentence. These places are also called functional places. The words or groups of words used at these functional places are called phrases. A typical noun phrase in Marathi may consist of: Determiner (optional), Adjective(s) (optional), Noun, Postpositions (equivalent of prepositions in English), Quantifiers (optional)

A noun phrase can contain determiners, adjectives and nouns. Determiners, adjectives and nouns join together in a specific order to form a noun phrase, which can be represented by a finite state automata graph as follows –

According to the above Finite State Automata (FSA), the number of determiners in a noun phrase can be zero or one, while adjectives can be zero or many. Here are some examples of Marathi noun phrases within sentences:

Here's Marathi noun phrases with different types of modifiers:

1. Head Noun Alone:

उदाहरण: मुलगा गातो. (Mulga gaato.) - The boy sings. ("मुलगा- boy - is the noun phrase here, consisting only of the head noun.)

उदाहरण: वपशवी टेबलावर आहे. (Pishvii tebalaavar aahe.) - The **bag** is on the table. ("वपशवी" – bag - is the noun phrase.)

2. Noun with an Adjective (ववशेषण - Visheshaan):

उदाहरण: मोठी मांजर आली. (Mothi manjar aali .) - A **big cat** came. ("मोठी मांजर" - big cat

- is the noun phrase. "मांजर" – cat - is the head noun, and "मोठी" - big - is the adjective.)

उदाहरण: वनळा सदरा सुंदर आहे. (nila sadraa sundar aahe.) - The **blue shirt** is beautiful. ("वनळा सदरा" – blue shirt - is the noun phrase.

"सदरा" – shirt - is the head noun, and "वनळा" – blue - is the adjective.)

3. Noun with a Possessive (सांबांवाचक - Sambandhvachak):

उदाहरण: माझी आई नोकरी करते. (Majhi aai nokri karte .) – My **mother** is working . ("माझीआई" - my mother - is the noun phrase. "आई" - mother - is the head noun, and "माझी" - my - is the possessive pronoun acting as a modifier.)

Other such Possessives are- माझा, माझी, माझे, माझ्या, माझां, आमचा, आमची, आमचे, आमच्या, आमचां, आपला, आपली, आपले, आपल्या, आपलां तुझा, तुझी, तुझे, तुझ्या, तुझां , तुम्हाला,

वतचे, वतची, वतचा, त्याचा, त्याची, त्याचे, त्याचां तुमचां, तुमचा, तुमचे, तुमच्या, तुमची, त्यांचा, त्यांची, त्यांचे, त्यांच्या etc.

उदाहरण: सीताची बांगडी सापडली. (Sitaachii bangdi saapadlii.) - Sita's **bangle** found. ("सीताची बांगडी" - Sita's bangle - is the noun phrase. "बांगडी" - bangle - is the head noun, and "सीताची" - Sita's - is the possessive form of the noun.)

Other such Possessives are - चा, ची, चे, च्या etc.

4. Noun with a Demonstrative (दशाक - Darshak):

उदाहरण: ती शाळा चांगली आहे. (Ti shala changli aahe.) - **That school** is good. ("ती

"शाळा" - that school - is the noun phrase.
"शाळा " - school - is the head noun, and
"ती" - that - is the demonstrative pronoun
acting as a modifier.)

उदाहरण: हा बांगला जुना आहे. (haa bangalaa
junaa aahe .) - **This bungalow** is old. ("हा
बांगला " - this bungalow - is the noun phrase.
"बांगला " - bungalow - is the head noun, and
"हा" - this - is the demonstrative pronoun.)
Other such Possessives are - तो ,ती ,ते,त्या,
हे, हा,ही, ह्या, etc.

5. Noun with a Quantifier

(सांख्यावाचक/परमाणवाचक

Sankhyavachak/Parimanvachak):

उदाहरण: काही मुली बोलत आहेत. (Kahii
muliiia bolat aahet.) - **Some girls** are talking .
("काही मुली " - some girls - is the noun phrase.
"मुली" – girls - is the head noun, and "काही" -
some - is the quantifier.)

उदाहरण: थोडी साखर आणा. (Thodii saakhar
aanaa.) – Bring **some sugar**. ("थोडी साखर" -
some sugar- is the noun phrase. " साखर " –
sugar - is the head noun, and "थोडी " - some - is
the quantifier.)

Other such Possessives are - थोडे, थोडी, थोड्या,
थोड्या, जरासे, इतके, इतकेसे, क्वं वचत, जास्त,
बरीच, अनेक, मूठभर, बोटभर, ववतभर, हातभर,
घरभर, गावभर, बहुतेक, वावाक, आाी,
पुरेसे, कमी, भरपूर, ढीग, खूप जास्त, अनेक,
दोन्ही, शेकडो, हजारो, प्रत्येक, एकतर etc.

6. Noun with another Noun acting as a Modifier (often indicating material or type):

उदाहरण: सोनेरी केस सुंदर वदसत आहेत. (Soneri
kes sundar disat aahet.) – Golden hair looks
beautiful. ("सोनेरी केस" – Golden hair - is the
noun phrase. " केस " - hair - is the head noun,
and "सोनेरी " – Golden - derived from the noun

"सोने " – gold - acts as an adjective modifier.)

उदाहरण: कागदी वपशवी द्या. (Kagdi pishvi
dya.) - Give me a paper bag. ("कागदी वपशवी
" – paper bag - is the noun phrase. "वपशवी" –
bag - is the head noun, and "कागदी" –
papered - derived from the *noun* "कागद" –
paper- acts as an adjective modifier.)

Other such Possessives are - तपवकरी केस,
नारां गी सूया, लोखांडी कढई वपतळी वदवा, दगडी
कोळसा, कापडी वपशवी, कातडी जोडे, तुपकट
भाांडे, तेलकट वाटी, कागदी वपशवी etc.

7. Noun with a Postpositional Phrase (शब्दयोगी अव्यय वाक्ांश - Shabdyogi Avyay Vakyaansh) acting as a Modifier:

उदाहरण: शाळेतील ववद्याथी हुशार आहेत.
(Shaaletiil vidyaarthi hushaar aahet.) - The
students from the school are intelligent.
("शाळेतील ववद्याथी" - students from the
school - is the noun phrase. "ववद्याथी" -
students - is the head noun, and "शाळेतील" -
from the school - which includes the
postposition "तील" - from/of - acts as a
modifier.)

उदाहरण: घराच्या समोरचा रस्ता रं द आहे.
(Gharachya magcha rasta shant aahe.) – The
road in front of the house is narrow .
("घराच्या समोरचा रस्ता" – road in front of the
house - is the noun phrase. "रस्ता" - road - is
the head noun, and "घराच्या समोरचा " –
in front of the house - which includes the
postposition "समोरचा" – in front - acts as a
modifier.)

Other such Possessives are- ...च्या मागचा,
...च्या पुढचा, ...च्या वरचा etc.

8. Complex Noun Phrases (combinations of the above):

उदाहरण: तुझ्या लहान बवहणीची नवीन कार खूप सुंदर आहे. (Tujhya lahan bahinichi navin car khup sundar aahe.) - **Your younger sister's new car is very beautiful.** ("तुझ्या लहान बवहणीची नवीन कार" - Your younger sister's new car - is a complex noun phrase with possessive "तुझ्या" (Your), adjective "लहान" (younger), possessive "बवहणीची" (sister's), and adjective "नवीन" (new) modifying the head noun "कार" (car)

In such type of complex sentences there can be one or more adjectives, possessives with noun to form a complex phrase.

5. Methodology for Noun Phrase Identification

The process of noun phrase formation is based on sequential grammar framework. For this task, it is important to identify word groups. Phrasal rules have been made for noun phrase group formation. Phrasal rules scan the sentence from left to right. The appropriate POS category of the sentence words is determined.

After this, all the words of the sentence and their POS category are included in the sentence scanning process. Based on this, various grammatical components are formed. The sequence of phrase rules plays an important role in the formation of these grammatical components. The sequence of phrase rules is from fewer words to rules with more words.

Noun phrase rules have been divided into the following categories –

1. Possessive pronoun and demonstrative pronoun group formation –

These are used as options in noun phrases. These pronouns can be noun phrases in any order and any one of these pronouns or both pronouns can be part of a noun phrase. For

the formation of these pronoun groups, the word group rules are applied to the appropriate sequences of words.

2. Numeral and Intensifier Group Formation–

Numeral and Intensifier words contain Numeral Adjective and Quantifier. Numerals have two parts – (1) **Indefinite Numerals:** This shows the quantity which is not definitely measured. For example- **या सगळ्यात** कोण पडणार ? (Some more examples of Indefinite Numerals *are* – many (**ढोबळ, अनेक, बहु, ववववा, पुष्कळ**) more (**अवाक**), some (**काही**), less (**कमी**) **सवा ववद्याथी परीक्षा देऊन वनघून गेले** (All the students left the exam), **आम्हाला सगळं समजतंय** (We understand everything) **एक याडड कापड/कपडांनी भरलेले अंगण** (one yard of cloth/a yard full of cloth) (2) **Definite Numerals-** These numerals are countable with fixed quantity. These numerals are of the following types (Guru, 2013) –

a. Qualitative

i. **Integer Indicators - एक, दोन, तीन, चार/one, two, three, four etc.**

ii. **Fraction Indicators - पूर्णा, आर्ा, एक चतुर्थांश, तीन चतुर्थांश, अडीच, दीड, पाऊण/quarter, quarter, one and a quarter, two and a half etc.**

Quarter/ $\frac{1}{4}$	पाव
Half / $\frac{1}{2}$	आर्ा
Three fourth $\frac{3}{4}$	पाऊण
Full	पूर्णा
One & quarter $1\frac{1}{4}$	सव्वा
One & half $1\frac{1}{2}$	दीड
Quarter to two $1\frac{3}{4}$	पावणे दोन
Two & quarter $2\frac{1}{4}$	सव्वा दोन
Two & half $2\frac{1}{2}$	अडीच
Quarter to three $2\frac{3}{4}$	पावणे तीन
Three & quarter $3\frac{1}{4}$	सव्वा तीन
Three & half $3\frac{1}{2}$	साडे तीन

b. Repetitive - पवहले, दुसरे, वतसरे/first, second, fourth

c. Ordinal - दुप्पट, वतप्पट, चौपट/double, triple, four times

d. Collective Indicators - दोन्ही, वतन्ही, चारही/both, three of three, four of four

e. Each Numeral - प्रत्येक/every

The quantifiers can occur individually or in a combination of the above types but if all types of quantifiers occur in a sentence then its order is something like this –

(Each Numeral) (non-integer) (integer) (repetitive) (ordinal) (collective)

“NCD” is the POS tag category for numeral adjective while “QTF” is the POS tag category for quantifier. “QTF” is related to quantity. For example, 9th, 90th, 10th, etc. will be tagged with QTF. Adding वा, to the numeric word determines masculine gender while adding वी to it will make it feminine gender and वे neutral (10th/दहावा, दहावी, दहावे, 8th/आठवा, आठवी, आठवे)

Numbers and punctuation marks are used in writing date and time.

For example, सकाळी 11 वाजून पंचवीस ममनटे (11:25 am), दुपारी दोन वाजता (2 pm) and

dates 22/04/2025, 22.04.2025, 22-04-2025, 22-एप्रिल-2025 etc. have POS category “NCD”.

Regular Expression can be used to identify all the above types of categories.

पंधरावे, पमहले, दुसरे /fiftieth, first, second etc. are placed in the POS category “NCD” of numeral nouns. It has been identified through the paradigm table.

Range – One/एक

एकट	Masculine	Feminine	Neutral
Singular	एकटा	एकटी	एकटं
Plural	एकटे	एकट्या	एकटें
पमहल			
Singular	पमहला	पमहली	पमहलं
Plural	पमहले	पमहल्या	पमहलें
एखाद	Masculine	Feminine	Neutral
Singular	एखादा	एखादी	एखादं
Plural	एखादे	एखाद्या	एखादे
एक	Masculine	Feminine	Neutral
	एका	एका	एका

2° Two/दोन

दुसर	Masculine	Feminine	Neutral
Singular	दुसरा	दुसरी	दुसरं
Plural	दुसरे	दुसऱ्याड	दुसरे
दोघ	Masculine	Feminine	Neutral
Singular	दोघा	दोघी	दोघं
Plural	दोघां	दोघीं	दोघें
दोन	दोन्ही	दोन्ही	दोन्ही

3. Three/तीन

तीसर	Masculine	Feminine	Neutral
Singular	तीसरा	तीसरी-@	तीसरे
Plural	तीसरे	तीसऱ्याड	तीसरे
तीघ	Masculine	Feminine	Neutral
Singular	मतघे	तीघी	तीघं
Plural	तीघां	तीघीं	तीघां
तीन	मतन्ही	मतन्ही	मतन्ही

4. Four/चार

चवथ	Masculine	Feminine	Neutral
Singular	चवथा	चवथी	चवथं
Plural	चवथे	चवथ्या	चवथे
चौघ	Masculine	Feminine	Neutral
Singular	चौघे	चौघी	चौघं
Plural	चौघां	चौघीं	चौघां
चार	चारी	चारी	चारी

5° Five/पाच

पाच	Masculine	Feminine	Neutral
Singular	पाचवा	पाचवी	पाचवे/पाचवं
Plural	पाचही	पाचही	पाचही
सहा	Masculine	Feminine	Neutral
Singular	सहावा	सहावी	सहावे/सहावं

Plural	सहाही	सहाही	सहाही
--------	-------	-------	-------

After 4 from number 5 some fixed suffixes occurs with number to form their masculine, feminine and neuter numbering. These suffixes are - वा/वी/व्या/ वं etc.(5th/पाचवा, 6th/सहावा, सतरावा, अठरावाetc.)

First/पमहला, Second/दुसरा, Third/तीसरा,
Fourth/चवथा, Fifth/पाचवा, Sixth/सहावा,
Eleventh/अकरावा, Hundredth/शंभरावा

Adjective and relational adjectives are present in noun group optionally. There are zero or more adjectives in noun group. Sometimes verb acts as the noun which is called Verb adjective in adjective group such as- धावणारा मुलगा/running boy, धावणारा छोटा मुलगा/running little boy. Verb adjective always comes before qualitative adjective.

There are many types of qualitative adjectives which are

time – new, old,
place – long, wide, high, low,
shape – round, oblique,
colour – red, yellow,
condition – lean, thin, heavy and
quality – true, lie, good, bad.

There is a definite order of these different types of qualitative adjectives.

numeral-place-time-shape-condition-colour-quality such as –

1. तीन वर्ड जूना मोठा जड लाल लाकडी टेबल माझ्या घरी आहे. (Three years old wide heavy red wooden table is in my house.)

There are some such relational words which join the noun behind it or the adjective used like a noun and the noun coming before it together(चा, ची, चे, च्या,चं,मागे,पुढे,वर,खाली,).

Its POS category has been kept as PSP<>REL. PSP<>REL works to join the words coming before and after it. The POS category of the word formed after joining is similar to the POS category of the word coming at the end. For example, the formation of –NNPP word group can be seen –

आयोध्येचा राजा राम

((अयोध्या [NNPL] चा [PSP<>REL] (राजा [JJ] राम [NNPP]) [NNPP]) [NNPP])

4. Noun and Pronoun –

Noun or Pronoun is an essential member of a noun group. Noun or Pronoun is the head of a noun group and is located at the right end of the group. After this, postposition and particles are placed in the particle category which is part of the noun group. They generally come after the postposition. Its POS category is specified as PRT.

Every component has a head word/term. Since Marathi is a head-end language, the head term of every component is always at the end of the group. The POS rank of the components is the same as the POS rank of the head term of the components. The process of formation of components is called chunking. Hence, every time during the sentence scan, some components are formed. The word groups thus formed and the remaining words which are not yet part of any word group will all form a word group in the next word scan. Thus, this process continues until the root node of the phrase is obtained.

The process of word grouping in the noun group finding system is 3-level. First of all, the process of formation of different types of groups is done on the basis of POS tag. In this, the sequence of phrase rules has been set using the **indexical grammar method**. During group formation, rules are executed in a fixed order due to which different components are formed by five types of chunking process. Noun group consists of five types of chunk sets. Noun group is obtained by adding these five sets. The words which take part in the formation of each chunk set cannot be a part of the chunk set formation in the next level process because these words are already members of some chunk set.

The words participating in each level will be those words which are not members of any chunk set till now and the chunk set tags formed in the previous level can also participate in the chunk set formation of the next level. In this way, chunk sets are formed at different levels. This process continues until the top tag NP of the noun group is obtained.

Flow chart of the process of noun phrase formation –

System Output :

The evaluation of the system on syntactic parameters was done by creating a confusion matrix for noun phrase (NP), adjective phrase (ADJP) and preposition parameters. The evaluation of the system on syntactic parameters was done by creating a confusion matrix for noun phrase (NP), adjective phrase (ADJP) and preposition phrase (PP). The percentage of precision, recall and F1-measure for each phrase was calculated from each confusion matrix. The F1-measure for noun phrase (NP), adjective phrase (ADJP) and preposition phrase (PP) was 0.92, 0.76, and 0.66 respectively. The

5. Evaluation and Conclusion:

The noun phrase detection system was tested on the development corpus of Marathi language. This corpus was developed by IIT Mumbai. The sentences selected for testing included simple, complex and compound sentences so that the system could be tested on all parameters. The evaluation of the system on syntactic parameters was done by creating a confusion matrix for noun phrase (NP), adjective phrase (ADJP) and preposition phrase (PP). The percentage of precision, recall and F1-measure for each phrase was

overall performance of the system was shown as 0.90

References

Books-

1. Murti, Kavinarayan(2005).Natural language Processing.New Delhi:Ess Publications.
2. वाळंबे,मो.रा.(2016).सुगम मराठी व्याकरण व लेखन.मुंबई:मनमतन िकाशन
3. वाळंबे,मो.रा.(2017).सुगम मराठी व्याकरण व लेखन.मुंबई:मनमतन िकाशन

Bharati Akshar, Chaitany Vinit, Sanghal Rajiv(1995).Natural Language Processing: A Paninian Perspective.PHI Publication

e-Books-

1. Bellairs,S.K.,Lakshmana,Y.Askhedkar.(2018). Grammar of the Marathi Language.
2. Chavan,Akshay.(2019).Complete Tutorial on Named Entity Recognition (NER) using Python and Keras.
3. दामळे,मोरो केशव.(2019).शास्त्रीय मराठी व्याकरण.<https://epustakalay.com/book>.
4. Franklin. Classics PUBLICATION.ISBN 0341688169.ISBN-13.
5. Gudivada,Venkat,Rao C.R.Computational Analysis and Understanding of Natural Languages:Principles, Methods and Applications.Volume 38.1st Edition.
6. कुलकर्णी,खंडेराव.(2019). मराठी व्याकरण स्वरूप व मचमकत्सा.पदमगंधा पब्लिकेशन ISBN No.9789386594501.

Research papers-

1. International Journal of Advanced Information Technology (IJAIT) Vol. 3, No.2, April2013
2. (tagset developed by IIIT Hyderabad (Bharti, et. al., 2006) [1].)
3. International Journal of Computer Applications (0975 – 8887) Volume 119 – No.18, June 2015 A part of speech (POS)Tagger for Marathi Language, Sharvari Govilkar, Department of Information Technology TSEC, Bandra, Mumbai, India Bakal J. W SJCOE , Dombivli, Thane India Shubhangi Rathod Department of Computer Engineering PIIT, New Panvel, India
4. Kumar,Ashish,Paul,Avinash.(2013).Text Mining with R eBook(Information Retrieval).Springer.
7. Lafferty,John.(2003).Language Modeling for Information Retrieval.ISBN-13.
8. Palanivelu,L.M.,N.Jayathi,S.Sadesh.(2013). INFORMATION RETRIEVAL.ISBN-13:978-93-86532-08-4.
10. Rajan,Annie,Salgaonkar Ambuja.(6/12/2021),ICT with Intelligent Applications(Named Entity Recognizer for Konkani Text).Springer.

5. Sekine,Satoshi,Elisabete,Ranchhod.Named Entities: Recognition, classification and use: 19 (Benjamins Current Topics).
6. Venu,Govindaraju,Vijay,Raghavan,C.R. Rao.Big Data Analytics.Volume 33.1st Edition.

Websites-

1. wikipedia.org/wiki/Named-entity_recognition
2. <https://monkeylearn.com/blog/named-entity-recognition>
3. <https://medium.com/mysupera/what-is-named-entity-recognition-ner-234>
4. https://www.tutorialspoint.com/opennlp/opennlp_named_entity_recognition
5. <https://nanonets.com/blog/named-entity-recognition-with-nltk-and-spacy>
6. <https://www.geeksforgeeks.org/nlp-proper-noun-extraction/>
7. www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1877050924009517
8. Discovering suffixes: A Case Study for Marathi Language - Semantic Scholar
9. http://web2py.iiit.ac.in/research_centres/publications/index
10. <https://blog.algorithmia.com/introduction-natural-language-processing-nlp/>
11. <http://www.cfilt.iitb.ac.in/Tools.html>
12. <http://www.cfilt.iitb.ac.in/~corpus/marathi/find.php?word=237>
13. <http://docs.cltk.org/en/latest/marathi.html>
14. <https://www.behindthename.com/names/usage/indian/3>